

JOB SECURITY AND WORK BEHAVIOURS: A SOCIOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE EMPLOYEES' ATTITUDE IN THE WORKPLACE IN MANUFACTURING ORGANIZATIONS IN NORTHERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Job security and work behaviour play some vital roles in any organisation's dynamics, objectives and general effectiveness. This study mainly examined the association between job security and employees' work behaviour in selected manufacturing organisations in Northern Nigeria. Social Bond Theory was equally adopted as a theoretical guide. Survey design was adopted using questionnaire and oral interview guide in generating data for the study. Using Taro Yamane (1967) formula, a sample of 403 respondents out of 27,500 populations were sampled from some selected organisations. For more reliable and comprehensive data, study complemented qualitative with qualitative data by interviewing 3 participants from each of these three organisations. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics while inferential analysis was adopted Chi-square analysis at 0.005 level of significance and content analysis for qualitative data. The study found that job security has a significant positive effect on work behaviours. Workers in these selected organisations were in constant fear of losing their jobs. It was also found that job insecurity could result in negative work behaviour as workers who feel insecure may develop psychological problems that may lead to a lack of concentration at work. It was concluded that the job performance and organisational citizenship culture of workers in the organisations remain intact even though job security is not encouraging and favourable. This is because they do not have any alternative jobs. The study recommended that there is a need for job security for employees to concentrate on their jobs for maximum productivity and overall performance of the organisation.

Keywords: - Job Security; Work Behaviour; Employees; Manufacturing Organisations

INTRODUCTION

Job security is one of the major factors that can help an organisation achieve its targeted objectives. Job security and work behaviour play vital roles in attaining the overall organisation's objectives and its general effectiveness. However, there are complicated issues that need attention.

Some studies examined the relationship between job security and the work behaviours of workers (Iji and Okpa, 2019; Alase and Akinbo, 2021). If workers are not certain about the security of their jobs (that is, if they think that they can be fired at any time), their work behaviours are likely to be negative as they show less commitment to their jobs (Somu, Joshi,

Nasurdin, Paramasivan and Tan, 2020; McKibbin and Fernando, 2020; Okafor and Afolabi, 2021). Existing studies showed that fear of the possibility of losing one's job at any time could adversely impact work behaviours (Nnaji-Ihedinmah, Osisoma and Ugwu, 2020; Ifeyinwa, Francisca, Peter and Rosemary, 2018). Workers who experience this fear are more likely to display a lukewarm attitude toward their jobs.

Amah (2018) study on the impact of job security on employees' performance, job satisfaction and management-employee relations of selected service marketing firms indicated that ensuring the job security of workers is one of the fundamental mechanisms for motivating workers to show appreciable level of job commitment and performance. Employees who feel that their jobs are secure are likely to perform better and show high loyalty and discipline (Ekhayemhe and Oguzie, 2018). Job security is essential for ensuring workers' positive work attitudes and behaviours (Ekhayemhe and Oguzie, 2018; Iji and Okpa, 2019; Alase and Akinbo, 2021).

Existing literature from Nigeria shows that job insecurity is reported to be higher in private organisations than in public organisations (Adeosun and Ohiani, 2020; Adeosun and Owolabi, 2021). The rate of hiring and firing is higher in private firms than in government firms. However, some private firms pay higher than some government firms (Adeosun and Owolabi, 2021). This may be the reason why some people prefer private firms to government firms (Adeosun and Ohiani, 2020). Nevertheless, those workers who consider job security more important than wage rate are motivated to display positive work behaviour by assuring them of job security (Ajani and Oyekola, 2019). Based on the review, it is evident that workers who are in

constant fear of losing their jobs are more likely to showcase negative work behaviours. The review suggests that job insecurity could result in negative work behaviour as workers who feel insecure in their jobs are more likely to develop mental health problems, hamper their socio-psychological well-being and reduce organisational performance since they are likely to be less focused and concentrated. However, workers with high levels of psychological capital can conveniently cope with job insecurity and concentrate more on their jobs. Based on this, the study assessed the effect of job security on work behaviour among employees of selected manufacturing organisations in North Central, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Some studies examined the relationship between job security and the work behaviours of workers (Iji and Okpa, 2019; Alase and Akinbo, 2021). If workers are not certain about the security of their jobs (that is, if they think that they can be fired at any time), their work behaviours are likely to be negative as they show less commitment to their jobs (Fernando, 2020; Rasdi et al., 2021). Existing studies showed that fear of the possibility of losing one's job at a time could adversely impact work behaviours (Nnaji-Ihedinmah, Osisoma and Ugwu, 2020; Ifeyinwa, Francisca, Peter and Rosemary, 2018). Workers who experience this fear are more likely to display lukewarm attitude to their jobs.

Hur and Perry (2020) study on the impact of job security on employees' performance, job satisfaction and management-employee relations of selected service marketing firms indicated that ensuring the job security of workers is one of the fundamental mechanisms for motivating workers to show appreciable level of job commitment and performance. Employees who feel that their jobs are secured are likely to perform better and show a high

level of loyalty and discipline on the jobs (Ekhayemhe and Oguzie, 2018). Job security is essential for ensuring positive work attitudes and behaviours of workers (Ekhayemhe and Oguzie, 2018; Iji and Okpa, 2019; Alase and Akinbo, 2021).

Nonetheless, some studies revealed that job security could destroy both the organisation and the employees (Adedapo, 2020; Nkedishu, 2020). Assuring workers of job security may make workers be too reliant and, thus, lose interest in career development. A worker who has lost interest in improving him/herself because of high sense of job security may exhibit adverse characteristics which may lead to poor performance, missing deadlines, reduced job commitments and overall poor productivity and service delivery. Nonetheless, literature shows that the relationship between job performance and job insecurity is still blurred (De Witte et al., 2016; Piccoli et al., 2021). Studies revealed that job security could put workers in distress and make their future uncertain (Ajani and Oyekola, 2019; Olayiwola, Abiona, Remilekun and Enobong, 2020). If workers face uncertainties in their jobs, their commitment and performance will be negatively affected (Hur and Perry, 2020). Uncertainties of the jobs may imply that their incomes will be less stable. Workers who perceived their work to be uncertain are more likely to be less focused on the jobs. They may not give their total concentration as they may be looking for more secure jobs since they can lose their current jobs any time.

Existing literature from Nigeria shows that job insecurity is reported to be higher in private organisations than public organisations (Adeosun and Ohiani, 2020; Adeosun and Owolabi, 2021). The rate of hiring and firing is high in private firms than government firms. However, some

private firms pay higher than some government firms (Adeosun and Owolabi, 2021). This may be the reason why some people prefer private firms to government firms (Adeosun and Ohiani, 2020). Nevertheless, those workers who consider job security important than wage rate are motivated to display positive work behaviour by assuring them of job security (Ajani and Oyekola, 2019). Based on the review, it is evident that workers who are in constant fear of losing their jobs are more likely to showcase negative work behaviours. The review suggests that job insecurity could result to negative work behaviour as workers who feel insecure in their jobs are more likely to develop mental health problem, hamper their socio-psychological wellbeing and reduce organizational performance since they are likely to be less focused and concentrated. However, workers with high level of psychological capital can conveniently cope with job insecurity and concentrate more on their jobs. Based on this, the study proposes that job security could lead to positive work behaviours.

METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional descriptive survey was used in this research to find out responses from the employees of the three selected manufacturing organisations in north central, Nigeria concerning how work culture affects workers' behaviour at the workplace. The data was collected and analysed. From the survey carried out by the researcher in 2021, the three manufacturing organisations total 27,500: Obajana cement (Kogi State), with 24,000, and Kam wire (Kwara State) with 3000. And OFL marbles (Nasarawa State) with 500.

With a total population of 27,500 from the three manufacturing organisations, a sample of 414 size was obtained using the Taro Yamane method. The Sampling procedure used was multi-stage sampling.

Purposive sampling was used to determine which organisation to sample from several manufacturing organisations from north central Nigeria; Quota sampling was used to determine how many employees to sample in each organisation, while purposive sampling was used to determine those to interview for the qualitative aspect. The data used for this study were both quantitative and qualitative, using the instrumentality of questionnaires and oral interviews. For quantitative, the researcher administered a questionnaire to 414 participants, of which 403 were returned. For qualitative, the researcher interviewed ten respondents from Obajana Cement, eight from KAM Industries and five from OFL Marble and Granites to learn more about the effect of job security on workers' behaviour at the workplace.

Test of Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between job security and the level of job performance among workers;
There is no significant relationship between job security and organisational citizenship behaviour among workers;

Data Analysis, Presentation, and Interpretation

The data for the study were analysed and results were presented. The organisation and presentation of data were done under three sections, namely, demographic data, research questions and testing of hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Respondents' Responses on Whether there is Job Security in their Organisations

This subsection presents quantitative results on job security in their organisations. From the results, 48.88 per cent (197) of the respondents strongly disagreed that they enjoy job security in their organisations; 13.89 per cent (56) of the respondents disagreed that they enjoy job security in their organisations; 13.15 per cent (53) of the respondents were undecided; 15.63 per cent (63) of the respondents agreed that they enjoy job security in their organisations; while 8.44 per cent (34) of the respondents strongly agreed that they enjoy job security in their organisations.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of the Respondents on Job Security

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Not highly secure	197	48.88
Not secure	56	13.89
Undecided	53	13.15
Secure	63	15.63
Highly secure	34	8.44
Total	403	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

From the results, about 65 per cent of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed that they enjoy job security in their organisations. This implies that employees are not sure of their job security. They can be fired on time. Literature shows

that a lack of job security could adversely impact job security. A study conducted by Amaechi, Eneh and Festus (2015) on the impact of job security on employees' performance, job satisfaction and management-employee relations of

selected service marketing firms revealed that job security is a critical motivational tool that could be used to improve the performance of employees as well as their loyalty and discipline. In other words, it is fundamental for ensuring positive work attitudes and behaviour of workers. However, some studies suggest that job security could also be harmful to both the organisation and the employees. It could make a worker to be too secure; thereby losing interest in career development (improving themselves in terms of skills). A worker who has lost interest in improving him/herself because of a high sense of job security may exhibit adverse characteristics which may lead to poor performance, missing deadlines, reduced job commitments and overall poor productivity and service delivery. It could be argued that job security could have positive and negative consequences for the organisation and employees. Nonetheless, literature shows that the relationship between job insecurity and job performance is still blurred (Muwardi, Saide, Indrajit, Iqbal, Astuti and Herzavina, 2020; Piccoli et al., 2021).

Also, qualitative analyses corroborate the above quantitative results. For instance, a participant expressed that:

Even though I am unhappy in this organisation, job security is important to me. The little we are getting here is something. We will know its value when it stops. At least we are better than those not working or getting stable incomes. Based on my experience, job security could bring about a relaxed atmosphere at the workplace because the workers will be calm and their jobs will be secure.

Another participant noted that:

I can concentrate on and build my

career if I feel that I may lose my job. If the organisation wants us to be more focused, the management has to assure us of job security and other work conditions. To my understanding, job insecurity means the perceived fear of losing the current job due to unexpected and uncontrollable events that can interfere with an employee's work experience. Our jobs are not secure in this organisation because it is private.

From the above results, it is evident that employees' jobs are not secure. This is expected given that most private organisations have a higher rate of job insecurity. Workers in the selected organisations are in constant fear of losing their jobs. Analysis suggests that job insecurity could result in negative work behaviour as workers who feel insecure in their jobs are more likely to develop mental health problems, hamper their socio-psychological well-being and reduce organisational performance since they are likely to be less focused and concentrated. However, workers with high levels of psychological capital can conveniently cope with job insecurity and concentrate more on their jobs.

Responses of the Respondents on Job Performance

In this subsection, quantitative results on the level of job performance are provided. From the results, 10.92 per cent (44) of the respondents argued that their job performance was very high; 5.46 per cent (22) of the respondents argued that their job performance was high; 16.62 per cent (80) of the respondents were undecided; 24.57 per cent (99) of the respondents argued that their job performance was low; 39.21 per cent (158) of the respondents argued that their job performance was very low.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of the Respondents on the Level of Job Performance

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very high	44	10.92
High	22	5.46
Undecided	80	16.62
Low	99	24.57
Very low	158	39.21
Total	403	100

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

From the Table above, about 65 per cent of the respondents argued that their job performance might be low or very low if the organisation fails to do the needful. This implies that the possibility of reduced job performance is high with poor and unfavourable working conditions. Low and very low job performance indicates negative work behaviour. Workers who work in enabling and favourable conditions are more likely to improve the quality and quantity of jobs performed, the accuracy and speed with which the work is performed and the overall effectiveness in performing the task. In most organisations, job performance determines promotion, rewards, giving responsibilities, freedom and independence. Existing studies revealed that job performance is likely to be reduced when the work conditions are unfavourable (Haryono, Rosady and MdSaad, 2018; Muwardi, Saide, Indrajit, Iqbal, Astuti and Herzavina, 2020). One study showed that favourable work conditions are correlated with job performance (Balducci, Alessandri, Zaniboni, Avanzi, Borgogni and Fraccaroli, 2021). It is only when workers are satisfied that they can perform better on the job. However, a study also showed a relationship between personality and job performance (Somu, Joshi, Nasurdin,

Paramasivan and Tan, 2020). The authors found that job performance depends on the personality of workers; thus downplaying the sociological and organisation-based factors influencing job performance. Other studies suggest that sociological, psychological and organisational factors determine work behaviours (Kutu and Olajide, 2020; Aqqad, Obeidat, Tarhini and Masa'deh, 2019).

Qualitative analysis revealed almost similar results. For instance, a participant stressed that:

Although our performance depends on the working conditions and other factors, I am working hard because this is a private organisation. If you don't perform, you may lose your job. I don't have any option but to give my best regardless of the work situation and other factors. If there were alternatives, I would have left this job

Another participant expressed that:

My job performance is determined by the nature of the machinery provided by the organisation. If we are provided with good machinery and enabling working conditions, our job performance is likely to improve. But I need to tell the truth: while we have enough machinery, our working conditions are bad. We are not happy here at all. The

organisation is not treating us well. We are just here doing the job because we do not have any means.

From the above quantitative and qualitative analyses, it is clear that the workers' job performance remains intact even though their working conditions are not encouraging and favourable. According to them, they are just working because they do not have any other alternatives. They have a limited voice to demand improvements in their working conditions. In summary, the likelihood of a decline in the job performance of workers is high if their working conditions are not favourable.

citizenship behaviour are presented in this subsection. From the results, 19.85 per cent (80) of the respondents argued that their organisational citizenship behaviour was very low; 16.13 per cent (65) of the respondents argued that their organisational citizenship behaviour was low; 24.81 per cent (100) of the respondents argued that their organisational citizenship behaviour is moderate (average); 20.10 per cent (80) of the respondents argued that their organisational citizenship behaviour was high; while 19.11 per cent (77) of the respondents argued that their organisational citizenship behaviour was very high.

Responses of the respondents on organisational citizenship behaviour: Quantitative results on organisational

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of the Respondents on Organisational Citizenship Behaviour

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very low	80	19.85
Low	65	16.13
Average	100	24.81
High	81	20.10
Very high	77	19.11
Total	403	100

Source: Researchers Field Survey, 2023

From the Table above, about 40 per cent of the respondents argued that their organisational citizenship behaviour is high and very high. Most of the employees argued that they are rendering help to their co-workers in a way that benefits the organisation. Studies indicated that the most important factors that could be used to explain citizenship behaviours are organisational justice and interpersonal relationships (Anwar, Mahmood, Yusliza, Ramayah, Faezah and Khalid, 2020; Mousa, Massoud and Ayoubi, 2020). Workers are more likely to show

citizenship behaviours if they have a good relationship with managers, managers always give support to them and managers always treat them fairly and equitably (Benuyenah, 2021). Literature also revealed that workers are more likely to exhibit citizenship behaviour if they feel attached to their peers and when they trust the people around them (Budur and Poturak, 2021; Ahmad, Ahmad, Islam and Kaleem, 2020). However, some studies noted that personality is one of the factors moderating and determining organisational citizenship behaviours (O'Grady, 2018;

Nazarian, Atkinson, Foroudi and Edirisinghe, 2020). These studies revealed that workers who are conscientious, agreeable, and low on neuroticism are more likely to exhibit and perform citizenship behaviours. Studies also show that those who are older are more likely to perform organisational citizenship behaviour (Mousa et al., 2020; Anwar et al., 2020).

Qualitative analysis revealed almost similar results. For instance, one participant expressed that:

I have been helping people in this organisation. I have been working here for like 20 years now. I have put many new workers through. I helped them to understand the policies and how things work in this organisation. I have volunteered to organize the company picnic several times. Also, I always offer advice to the management on how we can improve even though the management did not yield to most of my advice.

Another participant explained that:

I just like helping people. I help my colleagues to accomplish their tasks/jobs. I am doing the best I can for my colleagues even though I am not happy here. We are making ourselves happy by giving helping hands to one another. I am still managing to do what I can even though I don't have a good relationships with our manager. He is not supportive at all. He is not fair at all. I don't trust our

manager; I only trust a few of my colleagues. But I support and help any worker who needs my help regardless of whether they are trustworthy or nice or not. I think doing our job only is not enough; we need to include helping co-workers in a way that would help the organisation realize its goals.

From the results, the selected workers are still exhibiting and performing organisational citizenship behaviours even though the management (managers) appeared non-supportive. They feel that it is their social responsibility to help others, especially their co-workers. Their performance of organisational citizenship behaviours is helping the organisation to achieve its goals.

Test of Hypothesis

Test of Relationship between Job Security and the Level of Job Performance among Workers

To determine the relationship between job security and the level of job performance, the two variables are cross-tabulated. The frequency distributions of the variables are in Tables 1 and 2. From these Tables, several descriptive and statistical deductions are derived. The results show that there is a significant relationship between job security and the level of job performance ($X^2 = 41.11$, $df = 16$, at 0.05). This shows that the calculated Chi-square ($X^2 = 41.11$) is greater than the tabulated (critical value) ($X^2 = 26.296$) at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom of 16 (Table 4).

Table 4: Relationship between Job Security and Level of Performance

Job Security	Level of Performance					Total
	Very high	High	Undecided	Low	Very low	
Highly secure	06	2	12	2	12	34
Secure	11	4	08	13	27	63
Undecided	08	3	11	19	12	53
Not secure	10	5	06	21	14	56
Not highly secure	9	8	43	44	93	197
secure	44	22	80	99	158	403
Total						

X^2 (calculated value) = 41.11; df = 16; X^2 (critical value) = 26.296; Significance = 0.01; Pearson's R = 0.79

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient analysis showed a significant association between employees' perceptions of job security and their stated levels of job performance (0.79). Worker productivity rises as a result of increased assurance in one's job. This finding further validated the descriptive findings presented in Tables 1 and 2. Studies have shown that if employees are confident in their job security, they are more likely to perform well on the job (Haryono et al., 2018; Muwardi et al., 2020; Balducci et al., 2021; Somu et al., 2020). Security in one's employment is a key factor in fostering productivity in the workplace (Haryono et al., 2018; Somu et al., 2020).

Test of Relationship between Job Security and the Level of Organisation Citizenship Behaviours among Workers

To determine the relationship between job security and the display of organisational citizenship behaviour, the two variables are cross-tabulated. The frequency distributions of the variables are in Tables 1 and 3. From these Tables, several descriptive and statistical deductions are derived. The results show a significant relationship between job security and the level of organisational citizenship behaviour ($X^2 = 56.76$, df = 16, at 0.05). This shows that the calculated Chi-square ($X^2 = 56.76$) is greater than the tabulated (critical value) ($X^2 = 26.296$) at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom of 16 (see Table 5).

Table 5: Relationship between Job Security and the Display of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour

Job Security	Display of Organisational Citizenship Behaviours					Total
	Very high	High	Undecided	Low	Very low	
Highly secure	09	07	12	2	4	34
Secure	13	15	16	7	12	63
Undecided	11	12	11	4	15	53
Not secure	08	11	12	10	15	56
Not highly secure	36	36	49	42	34	197
secure	77	81	100	65	80	403
Total						

X^2 (calculated value) = 56.76; df = 16; X^2 (critical value) = 26.296; Significance = 0.03; Pearson's R = 0.64

Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient analysis showed a favourable association between job security and employees' stated levels of organisational citizenship behaviour ($r=0.64$). This suggests that when workers feel safe in their positions, they are more likely to act like good citizens of the company. The descriptive findings presented in Tables 1 and 3 were further validated by this finding. Positive organisational citizenship behaviours are more prevalent among employees who feel comfortable in their employment (Budur and Poturak, 2021; Ahmad, Ahmad, Islam and Kaleem, 2020; O'Grady, 2018; Nazarian, Atkinson, Foroudi and Edirisinghe, 2020). The next study will investigate how long people stay at their current jobs compared to how often they call in sick.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the job performance of the workers remains intact even though the working conditions are not encouraging and favourable. According to them, they are just working because they do not have any other alternatives. If they do not perform their jobs well, they are likely to lose their jobs since the organisations are private. They have a limited voice to demand improvements in their working conditions. The likelihood of a decline in the job performance of workers is high if their

working conditions are not favourable. From the results, the selected workers are still exhibiting and performing organisational citizenship behaviours even though the management (managers) appeared non-supportive. They feel that it is their social responsibility to help others, especially their co-workers. Their performance of organisational citizenship behaviours is helping the organisation to achieve its goals. It can also be argued that organisational citizenship behaviours could be determined by personality types. Some workers are friendly; while others are hostile. Those who are friendly are more likely to display and perform organisational citizenship behaviours than those who are hostile.

Recommendations

It is recommended that there is a need for job security. The results revealed that workers in the selected organisations are in constant fear of losing their jobs. Analysis suggests that job insecurity could result in negative work behaviour as workers who feel insecure in their jobs are more likely to develop mental health problems, hamper their socio-psychological well-being and reduce organisational performance since they are likely to be less focused and concentrated.

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